

Alliance Data Officers' Group Meeting

Tuesday 3rd September 2024, 10:30am to 12:00pm

This is a summary of the key points, outcomes and actions from the UK Health Data Research Alliance Data Officers' Group (DOG).

Summary of Actions

Actions	Lead
John Nolan to give more details on data curation in the next Data officers group meeting	Alliance Team
Call for Data officers to complete the gateway survey Gateway survey for data officers	Data Officers
Explore opportunity to integrate EMA metadata catalogue with HDR UK meta data catalogue	Alliance & technology team (Isaac Odiase and Chris Milner)
Circulate NHS data quality survey - Improving the quality of NHS data (office.com)	Alliance team

Welcome and Introductions

The Chair welcomed everyone, introduced himself, and encouraged participants to introduce themselves via the Teams chat. The Chair reminded participants of the aims of the Data Officers' group and proceeded to give an update on the UK Health Data Research Alliance.

1. Alliance Update (Geoff Hall)

HDR UK has welcomed four new organisations to the alliance, increasing membership to 107 UK organizations. The new members include the National PET Imaging Platform, NIHR Yorkshire and Humber Patient Safety Research Collaboration, Mother and Infant Research Electronic Data Analysis Programme, and the Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology, and Musculoskeletal Sciences (NDORMS). This expansion continues to strengthen the alliance's impact.

HDR UK has launched a Real-World Evidence (RWE) Network based on the OMOP common data model, with the coordination centre awarded to Dani Prieto-Alhambra and colleagues from NDORMS Oxford. HDR UK is also seeking seven data partners to join the RWE Network, and the deadline for the funding call has been extended to 10th September.

HDR UK will host the OHDSI UK meeting on 27th September at the Wellcome Trust in London. The event is currently sold out, but more tickets may become available, and individuals can register on the waiting list via Eventbrite.

2. Data Design Authority Update – Monica Jones (Associate Director HDR UK North)

Link: [Data Design Authority presentation slides.](#)

The Data Design Authority (DDA) has been established to ensure convergence in data standards across the Driver Programmes, particularly under the Usable Data pillar of the QQ2 project. The DDA, based on a model trialled in HDR UK North, aims to support and guide data initiatives, identifying shared challenges and encouraging collaborative solutions.

- **Data Principles Review:** The DDA discussed revisiting and aligning older data principles with current standards like OMOP and HL7 FHIR. The principles were drafted in 2020 and are due for revision to ensure they remain relevant.
- **Data Standards Updates:** Chris Orton and Lara Edwards are leading efforts to standardize data curation within the driver programmes. A systematic approach is being developed to streamline curation, with an ongoing review of disease and condition mapping.
- **Medicines Driver Programme:** Tony Brooks provided updates on the medicines mapping use case. Efforts are being made to align this with the broader UK data landscape, though it is currently unfunded.
- **Big Data for Complex Disease Programme:** John Nolan and Alexis Webb shared progress on data curation and product development. They have built tools like a dataset summary dashboard and a code list comparison tool to standardize work across the programme.

3. HDR UK innovation Gateway: Connecting Metadata Catalogues – Isaac Odiase (Gateway Chief Product Owner, HDR UK)

Link: [HDR Gateway Presentation Slide](#)

The presentation covered updates on the development of the Gateway, focusing on key enhancements and next steps. It highlighted improvements to the metadata onboarding process, allowing for manual onboarding through forms and JSON file uploads. The updates aim to make the Gateway cleaner and easier to use. New features include data linkage capabilities, progress tracking, and in-form guidance.

- **Two integration methods for metadata were introduced:** a private API and the HDR UK metadata integration. The preferred method for integration will be self-managed, reducing manual updates. Bulk uploads will not be available at launch but will be phased out in favour of integration.
- **New entities, such as Data Custodians and Data Custodian Network,** were introduced to improve discoverability and centralize datasets, tools, and publications for users. Teams will also be able to manage tools and scripts on the Gateway, with added functionality to link resources, improving the user experience.
- **The next steps include ongoing beta testing, a migration into pre-production, and a soft launch for data custodians.** A full launch of the MVP¹ Gateway will follow, depending on feedback and bug fixes during the soft launch. A survey link was provided to collect feedback from participants.

¹ Minimum Viable Product

4. **The HMA-EMA Catalogues of real-world data sources and studies: Facilitating Data Discoverability and Advancing Transparency of Real-World Evidence in EU Medicines Regulation – Stefania Simou (European Medicines Agency)**

[Link to Presentation](#)

This presentation was based on the recently launched catalogues of real-world data (RWD) sources and studies, which aim to enhance data discoverability and support regulatory decision-making within the European Medicines Agency (EMA). The initiative, stemming from the Big Data Steering Group, is part of a broader effort to optimise the use of big data in medicine regulation. [Homepage | HMA-EMA Catalogues of real-world data sources and studies \(europa.eu\)](#)

- The catalogues replace the older ENCePP resources database and the EU PAS register, offering a publicly accessible platform for regulators, researchers, and pharmaceutical companies. They provide metadata on RWD sources and non-interventional studies, fostering evidence-based decision-making and collaboration. The catalogues also link related studies and data sources, aiding study design, protocol evaluation, and result interpretation.
- Key features include enhanced search and export capabilities, user management via EU login, and automatic notifications on record updates. Future developments will involve expanding the platform to include veterinary data sources, integrating visualisation tools and dashboards, and improving interoperability with other systems.
- The platform is intended to support stakeholders in identifying suitable data sources for research, comparing data characteristics, and utilising metadata for studies. Its expansion will further facilitate data-driven discussions on drug safety and efficacy.

5. **Phenotyping Algorithm Development: Insight from exemplars – Sarah Lessels (British Heart Foundation Data Science Centre)**

[Link to presentation](#)

Insights were presented on the development of exemplar phenotyping algorithms, particularly in the context of cardiovascular and diabetes-related clinical trials. The discussion highlighted the complexity of linking large national datasets and the value of developing standardised algorithms for data-enabled trials.

- One project mentioned was SCORE-CVD, focused on Standardising outcome measures for cardiovascular diseases such as myocardial infarction (MI), stroke, heart failure, major bleeding, and cardiovascular death. A working group of clinical experts reviewed existing MI algorithms, incorporating feedback to refine the process. A key outcome was the decision not to include the ICD 10 I23 code, as it did not contribute significant new event data. The next steps involve applying the MI algorithm to a mock cohort and using it in ongoing clinical trials to compare treatment effects.
- For diabetes phenotyping, an algorithm was developed to define diabetes, diagnosis types, and create a cohort from available data. The use of a code list comparison tool was crucial in refining the algorithm, helping to identify and remove less accurate codes. Workshops with clinical experts and analysts proved invaluable in the algorithm's

development. The diabetes algorithm is currently being utilised by projects funded through the Diabetes Data Science Catalyst initiative.

6. Discussions

During the discussions, the EMA catalogue was recognized as a valuable resource for accessing real-world data (RWD), prompting a discussion on potential data exchange and interoperability with the HDRUK catalogue. A follow-up discussion was scheduled to explore integration, aiming to reduce duplication of effort and increase efficiency for users. The potential to provide access to both catalogues via a single portal was highlighted, which could streamline processes for researchers and regulators. Technical discussions, including potential API development, were identified as next steps.

After the presentation on Phenotyping Algorithms, it was noted that emergency departments often record suspected, rather than confirmed, diagnoses. This can cause long-term problems, as patients may continue to reference these unverified diagnoses, leading to confusion in future medical care.

The discussion then shifted to the diabetes algorithm, which could help accurately classify and code diabetic patients. A local hospital is looking to implement this algorithm to improve its coding system, ensuring that all diabetic patients are appropriately coded with SNOMED or ICD codes. A reclassification tool was also mentioned, which aims to track patients over time and adjust their diabetes classification accordingly.

Later, a contribution was made regarding work with a cardiac network on a coronary syndrome pathway. There was interest in further discussions about how this work could align with the ongoing data projects discussed.

AOB

Dates for upcoming meetings, including the Data Officers Group and OMOP Special Interest Group, are yet to be confirmed but will be circulated soon. Attendees were encouraged to join the OHDSI UK meeting on 27th September at the Wellcome Trust in London.

Attending Organisations

1. Action Against AMD
2. Barts Health NHS Trust
3. British Heart Foundation Data Science Centre
4. Cancer Research UK
5. Cystic Fibrosis
6. European Medicine Agency
7. Genomics England
8. Health and Social Care Northern Ireland
9. Health Data Research UK
10. Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust
11. Imperial College London
12. Intensive Care National Audit and Research Centre
13. Leeds Teaching Hospital
14. Medicine Discovery Catapult
15. National Health Service
16. National Institute of Health and Care Excellence
17. National Joint Registry
18. NHS Scotland
19. NHS Wales
20. NIHR BioResource
21. Nottinghamshire Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust
22. Optimum Patient Care
23. Our Future Health
24. Oxford Health NHS Foundation Trust
25. Research Data Scotland
26. Smart Data Research UK
27. TeckUK
28. The Brain Tumour Charity

29. The Royal Marsden NHS Trust

30. The University of Edinburgh

31. UK Kidney Foundation

32. University Birmingham NHS Foundation Trust

33. University of Aberdeen

34. University of Dundee

35. University of Leeds

36. University of Nottingham